

Supplemental Fig. S3

Human liver intralobular space

Human pancreas intralobular space

Supplemental Fig. S3 (related to **Fig. 4**). **Comparison of human liver and pancreas sympathetic innervation in the intralobular space.** Human liver (**A, B**; representative images); human pancreas (**C, D**; representative images). Green, sympathetic marker tyrosine hydroxylase; white, DAPI, nuclei. The same pixels (circle, area of interest) were extracted from the liver and pancreas images taken from a Zeiss LSM 800 microscope under a 25× LD LCI Plan-Apochromat objective (tile-scan mode with automatic image stitching) to perform the comparison. The number of pixels with the tyrosine hydroxylase signals were divided by those of the area of interest ×100% to estimate the sympathetic nerve density (**Fig. 4V**).